

Where Have All the Questions Gone?

An Analysis of Research Question Usage in Information Science Proceedings

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Abstract

This study originated from our teaching practice, where we guide students in developing research questions and research designs. Research method textbooks in Library and Information Science (LIS) highlight the importance of research questions. However, their use and formulation has not been explored within LIS research. We analyzed 402 accepted papers from an international information science conference between 2020 and 2024 to assess the presence and quantity of research questions or, alternatively, research aims. Each paper underwent a manual review for research questions, followed by both descriptive and qualitative content analysis. On average, half of the accepted papers do not include a formal research question, a trend that has remained consistent over the years regardless of the number of accepted papers or host countries. Most papers emphasize ‘what’ and ‘how’ questions. Additionally, all papers lacking a clear research question included a research aim or purpose statement, though these were generally less specific. This paper raises questions about the role and importance of research questions in LIS research. It also highlights an opportunity for the LIS community to establish clear expectations for both students and senior researchers.

Keywords: research questions; research design; education; Library and Information Science; research quality

1 Introduction

Likely, every higher education institution that offers a degree in information science emphasizes that graduate students structure their papers around a clear and well-defined research question. Research method textbooks in Library and Information Science (LIS) highlight the importance, usefulness and proper formulation of research questions (Connaway & Radford, 2016b; Given et al., 2023a). Additionally, conference review forms address the quality of submissions by asking if the research questions are well-defined.

Research questions are a must-have for many researchers with an information science education background, but as the field increasingly attracts researchers from a growing range of disciplines, not all consider research questions as fundamental (Thelwall & Mas-Bleda, 2020).

This article aims to explore the use of research questions in information science publications. Proceedings' articles of the iConferences were chosen, as this annual conference of the international iSchool community can be regarded as representative research in the LIS field, regarding diversity of topics and research methods. The article addresses the following two research questions:

RQ1 How many accepted papers at the iConference include a research question?

RQ2 What are typical research questions or research purposes found in these papers?

This article is organized as follows: We start by outlining the origins of the study's topic, followed by a review of relevant research on the study of research questions and trends. In the research design section, we detail the process of collecting empirical data through content analysis of papers published between 2020 and 2024. We then discuss the findings and their implications for this field.

2 Project Foundations

The introductory course in information science at the Berlin School of Library and Information Science at Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin is designed to familiarize master's students with current LIS topics and methods

and to prepare them for conducting their own research. Research questions are central to the final assessment at the end of the course. For the oral exam, each student is assigned a research question from an unpublished research paper in the LIS field. Their task is to develop a research design that would effectively address the question. For this assessment, students are not required to conduct the research, allowing them to focus on developing an ideal research design without considering practical constraints. In addition to assessing students' ability to design a viable research project, they are encouraged to critically reflect on the research question itself and its influence on their hypothetical project.

For these exams, we needed research questions that were unpublished at the time of the exam in mid-February but had been reviewed and deemed of high quality. Given the iConference's acceptance rate of less than 35%, it can be assumed that the research papers exemplify well-crafted research questions. The proceedings were published at the time of the iConference each March, with the proceedings nearly finalized but still unpublished in February. The iConference papers were thus selected as suitable candidates due to their relevant topics, the availability in unpublished, but accepted for publication form in mid-February and the quality of their research questions. This approach enabled students to compare their own research designs with the actual designs of the original publications after their exam. We submitted a formal request to the iSchool office and were granted access to the unpublished papers.

We manually checked the iConference papers for research questions, created a list of all research question per year and selected those that we deemed suitable and fair for our students. In the process of compiling these lists of potential research questions, it became clear that the use of research questions in the iConference proceedings was far from ubiquitous. This observation sparked our curiosity about the use of research questions in iConference proceedings over the five-year period from 2020 to 2024.

3 Literature Review

If we imagined ourselves as LIS students, beginning with the ideal textbook definition of research, what would we expect from a peer-reviewed article presented at a renowned international conference in our field? As students,

we may seek guidance and best practices to develop and plan our own research methods and writing. The literature from a variety of disciplines (Barroga & Matanguihan, 2022; Staller, 2022; White, 2013) and LIS textbooks provide information about research questions in the sections on the development of a research study (Connaway & Radford, 2016a) or research design (Given et al., 2023b). The optimal research process is described as a five-stage process, beginning with the development of a research problem and a research question (Given et al., 2023b). The research question should “determine the methodologies and methods used to collect and analyze the data” (Given et al., 2023b, p. 182). Connaway and Radford (2016a, p. 37) make a point to distinguish between the research question and a purpose statement. In their view a “research question is typically more precise and specific than a problem statement and that the purpose and problem for a research study are not interchangeable”. The textbook material highlights the significance of research questions and delineates the differences between a research gap, a research question and a research aim or purpose statement.

Despite the central role of research questions in research projects, surprisingly little has been published on this topic within LIS. In other fields, such as medicine, a few publications have explored research questions in various aspects, including their nature (Hosseini et al., 2024), their semantic structure (Miin-Hwa Lim & Luo, 2020), and the possibility of crowdsourcing them (Beck et al., 2022). The study by Thelwall and Mas-Bleda (2020) is particularly relevant, as it examines the use of research questions across a range of disciplines, providing an excellent summary of previous research. Their results indicate significant disciplinary differences in the prevalence of research questions across different fields. In some disciplines such as medical sciences or engineering, research questions are noticeably absent, whereas in others such as philosophy, theology or the social sciences, they are more prevalent. Their study diverges from the one presented here in two ways: First, it does not address LIS, which complicates direct comparisons. Second, their methodology relied on an automated data crawl from PubMed using the keyword “research question.” This approach purposefully excluded studies that used abbreviations like *RQI* or implicit research questions such as “this paper aims to study how X happens”.

Trends in LIS are commonly analyzed regarding bibliometric data, research topics (Dora & Kumar, 2020), use of theory (VanScoy et al., 2022), data sources (Armann-Keown & Patterson, 2020) or research methods. This analysis could focus on geographic regions (Gupta & Gul, 2024), topic areas

such as information behavior (Julien et al., 2011) or the proceedings of specific conferences such as ASIS&T (Islam & Agarwal, 2023). The iConference proceedings have been analyzed for bibliometric information, including authorship and collaboration (Jana & Pramanik, 2020) and in relation to review processes (Bogers & Greifeneder, 2016). However, the use of research questions in conference papers has not yet been explored within LIS research.

4 Method

This paper examines the use of research questions in the iConference proceedings from 2020 to 2024. The aim is to identify trends in the prevalence and quantity of research questions per paper. This analysis will offer insights into potential discrepancies between the theoretical guidelines for academic writing in LIS – particularly the structure and requirements of research papers as taught to students – and the actual writing practices of scholars in the field. It will also explore whether these practices have changed over time.

It is important to note that even within a relatively narrow academic field such as LIS, methodological approaches, academic practices, and writing styles can vary considerably. Each paper is distinct, and it is the responsibility of the author(s) to determine the most suitable type and style of presentation for their research. Research questions are one criteria of quality, but obviously not the only one.

As described above, we obtained access to all accepted full and short papers from each year of the iConference. We manually reviewed each paper to identify its research question, recording the questions in an Excel file along with the paper's abstract and title. Papers without a clear research question, or with questions deemed unsuitable for the oral exam, were excluded from the initial data collection for the oral exams. For the analysis of this paper, we validated the dataset by including any previously omitted papers and adding research purpose statements when a research question was missing. Two individuals independently coded the data using a deductive, descriptive coding approach, and descriptive statistics were applied for the analysis.

A manual content analysis was conducted, enabling the inclusion of all potential instances of research questions, including implicit ones and those using abbreviations. This approach also accounted for different question formulations, such as “The question that guides this research” or “the analysis focused on what is”. A clear distinction was made between the research question and the study’s aim, purpose, or goal, as the latter conveys the study’s intent but does not always pose a specific question. Examples of research aims include “this study was particularly interested in”, or “this paper uses the example of sharing private photos to explore the informational work of [...]”. During coding, we evaluated whether a research question could be identified, even if it was not explicitly stated. If no question could be determined, the paper was coded as lacking a research question, and its purpose or aim was recorded for further analysis. We also checked for the existence of research hypothesis, potentially as a substitute of research questions, but only five papers included a hypothesis and those also either had a research question or a research goal or aim. We therefore do not report separately on the use of hypothesis in this article.

In a second step, we coded the interrogative pronoun in all research questions. In a third and last step, we examined the wording of the research aims, focusing on the use of verbs that are used by authors to describe the focus of their article.

Our goal is not to cast a negative light on articles that did not include a research question, nor to single out papers with research questions or purpose statements that may be subject to critique. To avoid discrediting any specific work, we chose not to quote individual articles directly. Instead, we employed paraphrasing through obfuscation, altering the original wording while maintaining the intended meaning.

5 Findings

Between 2020 and 2024, a total of 402 articles were published in the iConference proceedings, with the number of accepted papers fluctuating each year (2020: 75; 2021: 91; 2022: 61; 2023: 84 and 2024: 91). All iConferences held in those years were either entirely virtual or had a significant virtual component and were hosted in various countries around the world (2020: Sweden; 2021: China; 2022: USA, Ireland, Japan; 2023: Spain, Australia and USA and 2024: China, Japan).

Approximately half of the papers (50.5%) did not include a research question in any form. Among those that did, the majority (46.3%) included 1–3 research questions, while only a small percentage (3.2%) featured more than four research questions (Table 1). Contrary to our assumption that increasing disciplinary diversity would lead to a noticeable trend in the use of research questions, no such pattern emerged (Table 2). The proportion of papers with research questions fluctuated between 46% and 54%, showing no clear correlation with the number of accepted papers or the iConference hosts.

Table 1: Number of research questions of the iConference articles from 2020 to 2024 (N = 402)

Number of research questions	% of papers
0 (no research question)	50.5%
1	12.9%
2	21.6%
3	11.7%
4	2.5%
5	0.2%
7	0.2%
11	0.2%

Table 2: The percentage of iConference papers including no research question from 2020 to 2024

Year of iConference proceedings	% of papers with no research question
2020 (75 papers)	48.0%
2021 (91 papers)	51.6%
2022 (61 papers)	50.8%
2023 (84 papers)	54.8%
2024 (91 papers)	46.2%

To identify typical research questions, we examined the use of interrogative pronouns, which help to indicate the focus of study in the field. These were coded for all 199 articles that included a research question. The pronoun “what” (47.7%) was by far the most used, followed by “how” (29.1%). Examples include: “What happens when institutions do”, “What is studied in conjunction with”, “What factors impact” and “How does the algorithm contribute to” or “How does the availability of information influence”. Table 3 lists other pronouns used and their frequencies.

Table 3:
Interrogative pronouns used in research questions and their frequencies

Interrogative pronoun	Frequency	Interrogative pronoun	Frequency
what	47.7%	who	1.0%
how	29.1%	degree to which	0.5%
do	4.0%	determine	0.5%
to what extent	3.5%	given	0.5%
which	2.5%	in what ways	0.5%
is	2.0%	was	0.5%
whether	2.0%	when	0.5%
are	1.5%	whose	0.5%
can	1.0%	why	0.5%
where	1.0%	will	0.5%

Table 4: Examples of paraphrased research aims and purposes stated in the 402 iConference papers.

Exploration and investigation	Applying methods
“Our primary objective is to understand the “this research aims to shed light on the impact of” “This paper surfaces issues related to” “this paper investigates the” “we study attention”	“The aim is to provide [...] with an approach to” “The purpose of this research is to apply” the [...] approach”
Comparison and evaluation	Developing tools
“The study aims to compare” “The purpose of this paper is to analyze the relationship between” “we evaluate the effectiveness”	“This paper explores a new tool” “The overall goal of our work is to develop”
Theoretical contributions	Sharing
“This paper offers a preliminary framework” “The aim of the paper is to make a theoretical contribution to” “we propose a knowledge representation model”	“we will share our experience and lessons learnt” “the purpose of this paper is to raise awareness of” “This paper reports on how [...] is being addressed”

Papers classified as lacking a research question were further analyzed based on the wording of their research aims, addressing research question 2. Authors described their aims in terms of exploration, investigation, compari-

son, or evaluation of various phenomena. Their goals included gaining a better understanding of phenomena, making theoretical contributions, applying specific approaches, developing tools, or proposing new models or frameworks and sharing experiences (see Table 4 for examples).

6 Discussion

The analysis reveals that the proportion of papers with a research question remains stable at around 50%. Although this may initially appear unfavorable, it is not as negative when compared to the findings of Thelwall and Mas-Bleda (2020). The central issue for discussion is thus not whether there is an increase or decrease in research questions during the last five years of iConferences. Instead, the focus should be on whether having 50% of papers without a clearly defined research question is an acceptable standard for the information science community.

Is it important for LIS to discuss the use of research questions? Some might argue that as long as the research design and analysis are rigorous, the absence of clear research questions or their vague formulation – such as terms like “*exploring*,” “*comparing*,” or “*applying a certain approach*” – is less critical. While experienced researchers may grasp the essence of a study without a specific research question, younger researchers often lack that implicit knowledge.

The absence of research questions provides authors with a figurative back door, making it more difficult for reviewers to critique the research design relative to the study’s purpose if that purpose is sufficiently vague (Staller, 2022). Addressing specific “*what*,” “*how*,” or “*why*” questions tends to be more challenging in research studies than addressing broader explorations or applications of models. A follow-up study analyzing the percentage of research questions in rejected iConference submissions would certainly be valuable.

Even if reviewers note the absence of a research question, it may only have a marginal impact on a paper’s acceptance. To the authors’ knowledge, the “soundness” criterion, which assesses the quality of a research question according to the guidelines, constitutes only 15% of the total score at the iConference. As a result, a lower score in soundness may not significantly affect the overall score. Increasing the weight of the soundness criterion in

the evaluation process could be an effective step toward encouraging the inclusion of more research questions.

7 Limitations

Despite our efforts to code research questions as inclusively as possible, some cases may still be open to interpretation. In such instances, we counted them as research questions to err on the side of inclusion, which means the actual number of papers without a research question could be higher.

The results of this analysis might differ if we had examined earlier years of the iConference, prior to the inclusion of virtual components, as these changes may have attracted different authors. Similarly, results might vary if we had analyzed a different conference or journal publications, which typically undergo a more rigorous revision process. Although iConference proceedings also involve revisions, to the authors' knowledge, no paper has been rejected after initial acceptance for failing to address reviewers' comments.

8 Conclusion

This study originated from our teaching practice, where we guide students in developing research questions for their projects. We analyzed 402 accepted papers from the iConference (2020–2024) to assess the presence and number of research questions, as well as, alternatively, research aims. We manually reviewed all papers for research questions and performed both descriptive and qualitative content analyses on examples of research questions and research aims.

The results indicate that, on average, half of the accepted iConference papers do not include a research question. This proportion remains stable over the years and is unaffected by the number of accepted papers or the host countries. Further analysis revealed that most papers with research questions focus on understanding “*what*” is happening and “*how*” it occurs.

All papers lacking a clear research question included at least a research aim or purpose statement. However, these statements are generally less precise about the study's focus compared to research questions. The purposes

vary widely, with the most common being explorations, evaluations, applications, or presentations of tools, models, or behaviors.

LIS students are taught that a strong research paper must include a well-defined research question, and they are penalized in term papers, master's theses, and doctoral dissertations if they fail to provide one. What impression must they have of their seniors when they encounter such practices in published papers?

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